

Paper 17

**THE GROWTH OF A SERVICE ORIENTED IT
COMPANY THROUGH OUTSOURCING –A CASE
STUDY OF INFOSYS LTD.**

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Abstract

Infosys Limited is an Indian multinational IT company, located its headquarters in Bengaluru, Karnataka, and established in the year 1981, which offers information technology, Business consulting and outsourcing services. It was founded by seven engineers with an investment of 250 dollars in India. In 2018-19, Infosys secured fifth rank Globally for IT services. Its brand value increased by 8% to \$6.5 billion. N. R. Narayanamurthy(CEO) was leading the company since its establishment till 2014, for 21 years. Its market cap amounted to 46.52 billion dollars on March 29, 2019. In 2019, it has 228,123 employees working at different roles and campus, all over the world. Infosys offers software development, maintenance, and autonomous validation services to finance, insurance, production, and other businesses. Infosys planned to reduce the amount of work done on site by their manpower travelling visas in the United States by shipping more work overseas. By this way, Infosys aim to protect and improve margin benefits. Charge for onsite projects are 3-4 times more than those delivered out of India. Infosys has nearly 25% work performed onsite and remaining from India. The company offers Insurance Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services. Infosys BPO secured first rank for offshore services. BPO was renamed as Infosys Business Process Management (BPM), in April 2002. Infosys BPM is meant for client's needs and fulfils them in a sustainable and complete manner. Forrester research has used Forrester wave methodology to classify Infosys as a leader in easy offshore capacities. The study also reviewed that Infosys, using a low-cost GDM or offshore delivery model, is the biggest of the six in terms of income for application-related services. This case study focused on various goals— business vs. operational metrics, profit vs. saving cost, and decreased service needs vs. better customer service. This Case study also helps to investigate the advantages of outsourcing (onshore and offshore) in terms of economic development and client demand.

Keywords: Infosys Limited, Offshore project, BPO, Forrester Wave Methodology, Application-related services.

1. Introduction

Infosys is a well-known multinational consulting and Information Technology Services Company founded in the year 1981. The firm mentioned in NASDAQ was constructed by

N.R. Narayanamurthy and six engineers with an initial investment of US\$ 250 [1]. With powerful business strategy and IT strength, it has grown to a US\$ 4.8 billion organization with market revenue of around 33 billion United States dollars. Infosys has spread its corporation globally by working in 28 countries, including America, the Middle East, Europe, Asia-Pacific, China and Africa. Infosys offers a range of services to improve and expand their growth in a competitive environment. Infosys clubs on-site high-quality consulting on business with off-site perfect execution of technology. This will finally decrease the cost of the full team of business experts to the client site. Application services enable the development, maintenance and modernisation of apps. Those services focus on offering best-quality apps, with less or easy maintenance. Services provided by Infosys BPO combines technology with knowledge of domain to produce processes on outsourcing. Infosys provides services to a wide spectrum of industries, including business functions, including finance, human resource management, data technology and other outsourcing domains [2]. This case study examines the problem of "performance measurement" with outsourcing with following goals: (1) to determine how Infosys benchmarks the inner performance of prospective providers ; (2) to determine how the service organization assesses the expenses of the outsourcing decision ; (3) to develop efficient performance policies to assess the outsourcing decision [2].

2. Vision and Mission

Infosys aims to provide best business solution by having efficient, best-in-class employees to become a standard corporation [3]. Infosys maintains their clients, employees and society with true care, sincerity and consideration to achieve their goals [3].

3. Background

The objective of this case study is to understand the decision-making process used by Infosys Ltd companies to outsource their IT operations [4]. Outsourcing means providing an external provider with the business activity. Outsourcing is based on a long-term, periodic relationship, where the provider is liable for the full outcomes of outsourcing activities. We see companies that have used outsourcing for their development, cost reduction, risk diversification or quality improvement [5-8]. There are only a few effective instances of offshoring, which has brought cost savings, innovation, quality improvement or other advantages, and these are mostly among big, globally engaged companies [9]. Outsourcing should be seen as an instrument that enables the company to focus on its key business. Based on the current growth in outsourcing (and also offshoring), backed by globalization, deregulation, the development of IT and communication techniques, advances in education and the deepening of specialization, we expect outsourcing to grow more and more [9-13].

4. Success saga

Table1: Success saga of Infosys [14]

Year	Milestone
1981	Year of establishment
1992	Transformed into a Public Limited company in India
1993	Received certification of ISO 9001/TickIT

1997	Achieved SEI - CMM Level 4
1999	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentioned in stock market NASDAQ • Reached \$100 Million in Annual revenues • Achieved SEI - CMM Level 5
2001	Reached 400 million dollars in revenues
2002	Succeeded to cross \$ half a billion in revenues
2004	Succeeded to cross \$ billion in revenues
2006	Succeeded to cross \$ 2 billion in revenues
2007	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reached 3 billion US dollars revenue. Employees count was more than 70,000 • Reported revenue of over 1 billion dollars in the second quarter.
2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Succeeded to receive 4.18 billion dollars revenue. • More than 1 billion dollars was the Annual net profit.
2009	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Global Dow considered company as a member. • Employee power reached more than 1,00,000.
2010	Obtained 5 billion dollars revenue
2011	Obtained 6 billion dollars revenue, and employee count reached 1,25,000.
2012	Made an entry on the NYSE market.
2016	Reached revenues of US\$10 billion.
2018	Successfully maintained 25 years on Indian Stock exchanges listing.
2019	Infosys BPM was honoured with Best CSR Practice Award

5. Strategies

Infosys' strategy is to strengthen the value of all its employees and constantly invest in the development of their skills [10-11]. Infosys strongly trusts that the major factor that helps them achieve development is their client-focused approach. Their strategy focuses on a limited number of reputable big organisations paying attention to product quality rather than concentrating on countless tiny organisations without concern for quality. Their strategy focuses on creating a picture rather than cost-differentiating model for quality driven model. It offers value-added alternatives to its new customers by providing deep industry knowledge. The company concentrates on emerging technologies and innovations. In recent years, they have added new services, like infrastructure management and, system integration which have increased the success of the company.

Infosys focuses on gaining the price benefit of their global delivery model [3]. Infosys has its vision on Modular Global Sourcing i.e., an evolutionary outsourcing approach, which enables an enterprise to implement best-of-breed sourcing approaches by structuring business processes and IT systems into individual modules. The main principles for Modular Global Sourcing include, taking an enterprise-wide perspective of aligning the sourcing objectives with the business strategy. The new idea of global outsourcing strategy will focus on what and when to consider outsourcing and also knows the managing skills to deliver the services globally throughout the value chain.

Infosys provides support across all sourcing and procurement management needs—from strategy formulation to BPM services and technology—providing comprehensive services. I.e. Infosys specialists outline the difficulties faced by procurement analytics and the holistic strategy required to resolve them. Fortunately, the combination of state-of-the-art visualization and artificial intelligence technology, coupled with models of 'as a service,' can

finally provide the insights needed for real business value. Procurement solutions are designed to provide access to sophisticated AI-based skills, allowing quicker decision-making [2].

6. Infosys Subsidiaries and Services offered [15]:

- 6.1 EdgeVerve Systems Limited: EdgeVerve Systems, Infosys' fully-owned subsidiary, creates and provides new software goods on-site or as cloud-hosted business platforms. Its headquarters are situated in Bengaluru, Electronic City. EdgeVerve is looking forward to announcing the 18.0 AssistEdge RPA. It offers services like banking, interactive business, distributive trade, credit service, enterprise purchasing service. It provides a universal solution used for banking, Finacle. 547 million clients of financial organization across 84 countries are choosing it.
- 6.2 Infosys BPM Limited: It is an outsourcing business process subsidiary. Infosys BPM provide its customers with transformative advantages through cost reduction, continuing productivity improvements, and process reengineering. It offers services on Human Resource, Finance & Accounting, Legal Process, Sales and Fulfilment, Sourcing and Procurement, Business Transformation Services, BPM Analytics, and Robotic Process Automation using outsourcing [7]. As of June 2019, Infosys BPM operates in India and 16 countries with 32 delivery centers across 5 continents. It provides job for 38,886 people from more than 100 nations.
- 6.3 Infosys Consulting services: It was established in 2004. Infosys Consulting is a worldwide consultant to lead businesses in strategizing, process engineering and managing transformation programs that are enabled by technology. By combining creative and human-focused strategies with the new hi-tech developments, allow organisations to rethink their future and generate viable and sustainable company value for automotive, insurance, life sciences, energy, resources, and financial services, etc. Globally, it offers its services to more than 200 active customers.
- 6.4 Infosys Public Services Inc: U.S.-based Infosys subsidiary, offers service in business consulting and technology solutions. Infosys partner with public sector organisations in the US and Canada. In Rockville, Maryland, it has opened its new headquarters and delivery centre. Digitizing customer experience and ensuring optimal service delivery by adopting innovative technologies through rapid innovation. It provides services to the public such as consulting services, technology services, company mobility, cloud and infrastructure, cyber and safety, legacy modernization, procurement modernization analytics and insights, digital ERP services.
- 6.5 Panaya : It was established in 2006. Delaware Corporation in the United States, is a major provider of automation technology for large-scale enterprise software management. It is software as a service company (SaaS). It is present across Americas, the EMEA and Asia. Infosys fully acquired the Panaya group of companies in 2015.
- 6.6 Skava: Skava is one of the major providers of mobile and multi-touch point solutions to many of the top retailers in the US. The Skava platform transforms its e-commerce platform to mobile web, tablet, Facebook and in-store technologies. Skava has been a pioneer in app growth since 2002. The first retail location is

fully optimized for tablets (t.staples.com) and works with various retailers to develop their in-store technology solutions.

6.7 Noah Consulting, LLC, a leading subsidiary of sophisticated information management consulting services. This firm assists upstream oil and gas businesses to provide worldwide technology and outsourcing services to oil and gas customers.

7. Financial Growth

Infosys annual revenue history and growth rate, for the financial year from 2015 to 2019 is shown below [16-18].

Table 2: Annual revenue of Infosys from financial year 2015 to 2019

Parameter	Mar15	Mar16	Mar17	Mar18	Mar19
Revenue	533,190	624,410	684,840	705,220	826,750
Cost of revenue	- 353,300	419,350	-466,360	-485,870	- 581,290
Gross Profit	179,890	205,060	218,480	219,350	245,460
Sales, general & administrative	-28,990	-32,760	-32,440	-29,240	-36,550
Depreciation	-10,170	-12,660	-17,030	-18,630	-20,110
Provision	0	0	0	0	0
Other operating income or expenses	-2190	-1100	0	0	-2,700
operational income	138,540	158,540	169,010	171,480	186,100
Expense Interest	0	0	0	0	0
Other income or expense	34,300	31,280	30,800	31,930	24,310
Profit before tax	172,840	189,820	199,810	203,410	210,410
Income tax & other taxes	49,110	53,010	55,980	42,410	56,310
Net income from continuing operations	123,730	136,810	143,830	161,000	154,100
Extraordinary & discontinued ops	0	0	0	0	0
Associates Share	-10	-30	-300	-710	0
Interest of Minority	0	0	0	0	-60
Net Income	123,720	136,780	143,530	160,290	154,040
Net income after preferred Dividend and others	123,720	136,780	143,530	160,290	154,040
Basic shares	4,571	4,571	4,571	4,511	4,347
Diluted Shares	4,571	4,571	4,573	4,515	4,353
EPS Basic	27.06	29.92	31.40	35.54	35.43
EPS Diluted	27.06	29.92	31.39	35.50	35.38

The graph shown in Fig. 1 depicts that company has consistent profit margins [17]. The overall performance, i.e. income and profit of Infosys are also rising, as shown in Fig 2[17].

Fig 1: Gross, Operating, Net Profit

Fig 2: Company performance chart

8. Competitors

Infosys’ major competitors are Accenture, Wipro and TCS. As of July 2019, Infosys had 841.6 K followers on Facebook and 235.5 K followers on Twitter. Infosys has revenues of \$11.8B and 228,000 staff [19]. Accenture, Wipro, CTS, TCS, IBM, Deloitte, Capgemini, Tech Mahindra, HP and HCL are the top 10 competitors in Infosys' competitive set. Together, more than 48.7 million of their approximately 2.4 million staff has increased. Infosys has 228,000 employees and ranks 6th among its top 10 competitors. The top 10 rivals are on average 235,653[18-19].

Table 3: Top10 competitor lists of Infosys

Ranking	IT Company	Workforce	Funding	Revenue
	Infosys	228,000	\$0	\$11.8B
1	Accenture	459,000	--	\$43.3B
2	Wipro	150,000	--	\$8.5B
3	Cognizant	281,600	\$29.2M	\$16.5B
4.	TCS	378,497	--	\$908.8M
5	IBM	350,600	--	\$77.9B
6	Deloitte	286,200	\$19.5M	\$43.2B
7	Capgemini	204,904	--	\$15.1B
8	Tech Mahindra	78,304	--	\$5.1B
9	Hp	55,000	\$538	\$58.7B
10	HCL	120,081	--	\$8.1B

Infosys’ revenue is ranked 7th among its top 10 rivals. The top 10 rivals are on average 26.3B. Infosys’ income increased by 10.4 percent over the last three quarters. Specifically, income was \$3.2B in first quarter 2019; income was \$3.2B in fourth quarter 2018; income was \$2.9B in third quarter 2018 [19].

9. Major Acquisitions

Table 4: Acquisitions of Infosys [22]

Acquired company	Located in	Cost	Date	Services of acquired company
Expert Information Services	Australia	23 million	December 2003	IT service
McCamish Systems	USA	\$38 million	December 2009	Insurance and financial

Portland Group	Australia	AUD 37 million	January 2012	Strategic sourcing and category management
Lodestone Holding AG	Switzerland	US\$345 million	September 2012	Management consultancy
Panaya	Israel	US\$200 million	March 2015	Automation technology
Skava	USA	US\$120 million	April 2015	Digital experience solutions
Noah-Consulting	USA	US\$70 million	November 2015	Information management consulting
Skytree	USA	Undisclosed amount	April 2017	Machine learning
Brilliant Basics	UK	GBP 7.5 million	August 2017	Product design and customer experience
Fluidio	Finland	EUR 65 million	October 2018	Sales force advisor and consulting partner
WongDoody	USA	US\$75 million	January 2019	Advertising and creative strategy
Stater	Netherlands	EUR 127.5 million	April 2019	Mortgage services

10. Corporate Structure

Since its establishment in 1981 till 2019, Infosys has 104 executives and 14 subsidiaries and its main 34 executives are shown in the given organizational chart [20-21].

Fig 3: Infosys Organizational Structure

11. Important Clients

Infosys provides next-generation digital services and consulting and became a leader worldwide. In 45 countries it has around 1,336 happy consumers to pilot their digital change [23].

12. SWOC Analysis

Table 5: Infosys SWOC analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost reduction. • Offers end to end business solutions • Strategic Association with giant companies like Amazon, IBM, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited markets • Few coverage of growing markets • Huge dependency on Europe and North America

Microsoft <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Delivery Model • Strong Focus On Innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High rate of attrition
Opportunities	Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest in young technology businesses • Expansion in spending on digital technology • New Technologies • Increased need for cloud based approaches • Focus on promising markets • IT integration across Industries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong rivalry • Changes in US migration laws • Employee retention.

13. Green Initiatives

Environmental conservation is responsible for creating a better world both for today and for the future. Infosys wants to be identified as a business committed to high standards of environmental management by all stakeholders, including clients, staff, suppliers, share holders and the wider community. Infosys has more concern on its contractors, advisors and staff with a secure and healthy environment. Infosys considers each means of decreasing carbon trace, water usage and power use. Infosys has taken initiatives on Green Infrastructure, Energy Conservation, Water Sustainability, Biodiversity Conservation and Promotion, Waste Management and Green Innovation. Because of its commitment to use renewable energy, in May 2015, Infosys was qualified to join the RE100 renewable energy campaign [24].

14. Stakeholders and corporate social responsibility initiatives

Clients, employees, investors, vendors or partners, government and local communities are the stakeholders of Infosys. Sustainable development of the communities in which it operates is an important part of its CSR [24]. It focuses on education, health care, arts and culture, rural development. Infosys Limited, a digital service and consulting conglomerate, has spent Rs. 342 crore against its prescribed CSR spending of Rs. 340 crore (2 percent of net profit of Rs. 17,018 Cr) on multiple CSR schemes as provided for in Section 135 of the Act [24].

15. Conclusion

This case study explores that Infosys work on its strategies with new ideas of information technology to reach each and every customer on their own way. With their strategic planning and leadership, Infosys has worked hard and even managed to remain competitive even in the era of a worldwide financial downturn. They still need to concentrate on inner and external variables that help to win the weakness and challenges [23][25]. It is very evident that Infosys services will play a significant part in their overall income. That is to say, 31.6% of its total income from economic services, 15.9% from retail, 13.5% from communications, 12.7% from energy, utilities, infrastructure and services, 10% from manufacturing, 7.7% from hi-tech and 6% from life sciences[26]. By outsourcing its services worldwide, i.e. 2.3 percent from India, 24 percent from Europe, 61.2 percent from North America and 12.5 percent from the rest of the globe, Infosys obtained its total revenue. Also Infosys increased their employees count from 2,04,107 (March 2018) to 2,28,123(in March 2019) [26]. Outsourcing may be used to improve cost, quality, and service and time-to-market effectiveness.

16. Future plans

Infosys focuses on innovative digital techniques to make the correct choices to enhance its efficiency in order to achieve its goals. The firm also intends to expand its workforce in the US, its biggest market. It announced a plan to employ 10,000 Americans in the United States [23]. Digital labour management, process re-engineering, talent and value chain sharing innovation—these are future outsourcing opportunities.

17. References

- [1] Guragain, N., & Vanja, S. (2019, July 7). Infosys Success: From Borrowed \$250 To Global IT Giant. Retrieved from <https://brandriddle.com/infosys-from-borrowed-250-to-global-it-giant/>, Retrieved- on 10/08/2019
- [2] Moorthi, Y. (2011). Non-linear growth: The road ahead for Indian IT outsourcing companies. *IIMB Management Review*, 23(2),91–101. doi:10.1016/j.iimb.2011.04.009
- [3] (n.d.). Vision And Mission Of Infosys In Consulting And It Services Business Essay. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/business/vision-and-mission-of-infosys-in-consulting-and-it-services-business-essay.php>
- [4] Arora, A., V. S. Arunachalam, J. Asundi and F. Ronald, 2000. “The Indian software services industry”, *Research Policy*, vol. 30, pp. 1267-1287.
- [5] Patel, D. (2017, July 17). The Pros And Cons Of Outsourcing. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/deeppatel/2017/07/17/the-pros-and-cons-of-outsourcing-and-the-effect-on-company-culture/>. Retrieved- on 31/08/2019
- [6] (n.d.). A Study of Performance Measurement in the Outsourcing Decision. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/book/9781856176804/a-study-of-performance-measurement-in-the-outsourcing-decision>. Retrieved- on 20/08/2019
- [7] Mcivor, R., Humphreys, P., Mckittrick, A., & Wall, T. (2009). Performance management and the outsourcing process. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 29(10), 1025–1048. doi: 10.1108/01443570910993474
- [8] Soltanifar, M. (2016). Infosys: A Case Study on Becoming a Global Brand in Consulting Technology and Outsourcing Solutions. *Multinational Management*, 149–170. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-23012-2_9
- [9] Heeks, R., 1996. “India’s Software Industry: State Policy, Liberalization and Industrial Development”, *Sage Publications*, New Delhi, Thousand Oaks, London.
- [10] Narayanamurthy, N. R., 2000. “Making India a significant IT player in this millennium”, in Romila Thapar (ed.), *India: Another Millennium*, New Delhi: Viking and Penguin Books.
- [11] Schware, R. (1992). Software industry entry strategies for developing countries: A “walking on two legs” proposition. *World Development*, 20(2), 143–164. doi: 10.1016/0305-750x(92)90096-e
- [12] Secretariat, U. (1992). Enhancing Competitiveness of Potential Export Sectors in Developing Countries--Lessons from Experience. *Foreign Trade Review*, 27(3), 305–317. doi: 10.1177/0015732515920306
- [13] Rouse, A. C. (2010). Managing E-Collaboration Risks in Business Process Outsourcing. *IT Outsourcing*, 1648–1655. doi: 10.4018/978-1-60566-770-6.ch104
- [14] Standard, B. (n.d.). Infosys Ltd. Retrieved from <https://www.business-standard.com/company/infosys-2806/information/company-history>.

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- [15] Infosys Limited. (n.d.). Subsidiaries. Retrieved from <https://www.infosys.com/about/Pages/subsidiaries.aspx>, Retrieved- on 15/08/2019
- [16] (n.d.). Infosys Total Assets 2006-2019: INFY. Retrieved from <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks/charts/INFY/infosys/total-assets>
- [17] (n.d.).Craytheon.Retrieved from https://craytheon.com/financials/fundamental_stock_analysis_cagr_annual_growth_rate_trend_chart.php?company=INFY ,Retrieved- on 20/08/2019
- [18] (n.d.). Home. Retrieved from <https://finshiksha.com/finshiksha-quick-company-analysis-it-sector-in-india-infosys-ltd/>, Retrieved- on 12/08/2019
- [19] (n.d.). Infosys Competitors, Revenue and Employees - Owler Company Profile. Retrieved from <https://www.owler.com/company/infosys>, Retrieved- on 20/08/2019.
- [20] (n.d.). onkarsule. Retrieved from <https://onkarsule.files.wordpress.com/> Retrieved- on 29/08/2019
- [21] (n.d.). Org Chart Infosys. Retrieved from <https://www.theofficialboard.com/org-chart/infosys>
- [22] (2019, August 28). Infosys. Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infosys>
- [23] Mendonca, J., & Pramanik, A. (2019, February 28). Infosys sees cloud & analytics as future billion-dollar units. Retrieved from <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/tech/infosys-sees-cloud-analytics-as-future-billion-dollar-units/articleshow/68194524.cms?from=mdr>, Retrieved- on 21/08/2019
- [24] Infosys Limited. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.infosys.com/sustainability>, Retrieved- on 10/08/2019
- [25] Gupta, S., & Dzharova, H. (2014). Innovation and adaptation: Continuing the infosys journey In conversation with S. D. Shibulal, co-founder, CEO & Managing Director, Infosys. *IIMB Management Review*, 26(4), 212. doi: 10.1016/j.iimb.2014.10.006
- [26] Infotech. (2019, April 13). Infosys achieves \$1.035 billion digital revenues. Retrieved from <https://infotechlead.com/bpo/infosys-achieves-1-035-billion-digital-revenues-58235>
- [27] Madhushree.,Revathi R, Anil Kumar, & Aithal P.S., (2018). Business Strategy of Top Indian IT Company: MindTree. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 22-36.